

Studies on the Effect of Humic Acid in the Fixation of Added Ammonium in Some Soils of West Bengal

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The effect of humic acid in the fixation of added NH_4^+ in six soils of West Bengal has been studied. The addition of humic acid decreased the fixation of NH_4^+ in the hydrogen peroxide treated soils. The fixation of NH_4^+ in the hydrogen peroxide untreated soils was greater than in the cases of hydrogen peroxide treated soils. But the addition of humic acid to the untreated soils greatly hindered the fixation.

It has now been well established that ammonium ion applied as salts of strong acids to soils is rapidly incorporated into the organic and inorganic fractions of the soils and are unavailable to plants. The retention and fixation of ammonium ion have been studied by different workers¹⁻³. They have shown that clay minerals of the 1:1 type or kaolin group fix little NH_4^+ . In the 2:1 type of clay, minerals such as montmorillonite, vermiculite, illite vary in their ability to fix ammonium⁴⁻⁶. Ammonium can be fixed as a result of chemical interaction between soils and ammonium applied as aqueous ammonia, ammonia gas or ammonium salts⁷⁻⁹. The rate of fixation depends not only on the mineralogical status of the soils but also on the C/N ratio and other soil factors such as temperature, pH and chemical form of available nitrogen¹⁰⁻¹³.

Since organic and inorganic fractions of the soils fix ammonium in different mechanisms, it was felt necessary to study the effect of one fraction to

of added ammonium in presence and in absence of humic acid.

Experimental

Six soil samples (0-22 cm depth) collected from different agroclimatic regions of West Bengal were used in the experiment. The relevant characteristics of the soils are given in Table 1.

5 g portions of air dried, ground soil in duplicate were taken in glass tubes in two series. In one series 0.025 g and in the second 0.05 g of pure dialysed humic acid were added. 100 ppm nitrogen in the form of ammonium sulphate was then added to each tube and the soil was moistened with distilled water to ensure its 50 per cent moisture holding capacity. The tubes were stoppered and incubated for 15 and 30 days at room temperature and fixed ammonium was determined in duplicate by the method of Silva and Bremner¹⁴.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS

Soils	pH	Sp. conductance mmhos/cm	Organic carbon (%)	Total N (%)	C.E.C. me/100 gms	Native fixed NH_4^+ N ppm	Clay %	Silt %	Sand %	Dominant clay minerals
Sriniketan	6.15	0.071	0.290	0.029	7.9	161.0	17.0	10.0	71.1	Kaolinite
Bankura	5.30	0.170	0.114	0.010	8.6	149.8	18.5	21.6	60.7	Illite
North Bengal	4.80	0.412	1.618	0.098	18.7	176.4	26.7	24.9	48.4	,
Canning	6.40	4.686	0.807	0.097	18.6	212.5	42.0	43.0	14.5	,
Kalyani	6.65	0.284	1.083	0.136	32.8	339.8	47.0	23.5	26.5	,
Chinsurah	7.10	0.362	0.955	0.096	33.5	327.2	54.2	28.1	17.7	,

another on the fixation process. The present investigation, therefore, deals with the study on the fixation

In another set of experiments, the soils were treated with 6 per cent hydrogen peroxide repeatedly to remove the native organic matter. The soils were then dried and ground. 5 g portions of these hydrogen peroxide treated soils were taken in glass

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tubes and same treatments as above were made and fixed ammonium was determined in each case in two different incubation periods.

Humic acid was extracted from Dehradun soil. The method of extraction and purification has been described earlier¹⁵. The physicochemical properties of the soils have been determined by standard conventional methods¹⁶.

Results and Discussion

The amount of NH_4^+ fixed by organic matter free soils is given in Table 2. As these soils are free from organic matter, the amount of NH_4^+ fixed depends solely on the amount of clay and the nature of the clay minerals.

TABLE 2—FIXED $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ AS PERCENTAGE OF THE ADDED NITROGEN IN HYDROGEN PEROXIDE TREATED AND UNTREATED SOILS

Soils	Treatments	Treated soils		Untreated soils	
		Days of incubation		Days of incubation	
		15 days	30 days	15 days	30 days
Sriniketan	A	23.90	26.50	28.00	30.60
	B	18.60	20.80	23.20	25.40
	C	17.00	20.00	20.40	21.50
Bankura	A	20.70	24.50	26.30	29.70
	B	16.20	18.60	22.50	26.80
	C	14.80	17.00	22.00	25.20
North Bengal	A	34.40	38.00	39.50	40.80
	B	29.00	32.50	34.10	36.30
	C	26.50	30.60	32.60	33.80
Canning	A	37.60	41.20	42.00	45.80
	B	35.20	38.00	37.40	40.60
	C	31.30	32.60	37.00	40.00
Kalyani	A	43.20	47.80	50.20	53.60
	B	39.50	42.50	43.80	47.00
	C	38.00	41.00	41.60	45.80
Chinsurah	A	45.30	48.60	50.60	58.40
	B	40.80	42.80	41.80	44.50
	C	35.00	36.00	38.20	40.80

A = 100 ppm of N; B = A+0.5% humic acid;
C = A+1.0% humic acid.

Sriniketan soil containing a large amount of sand (71.1%) and the clay minerals being predominantly kaolinite, fixed a small amount of added NH_4^+ . With the increase of the incubation period fixation did not increase so much. The addition of humic acid decreased the fixation and with the increase of the incubation period there was a slight increase of fixation. The fixation further decreased when a greater amount of humic acid was added. The same sequence was followed in almost every case.

Table 2 shows that the soils of Kalyani, Chinsurah, Canning and North Bengal fixed greater amount of NH_4^+ than that of Sriniketan and Bankura soils because the former contains greater amount of clay fraction and the clay minerals present in them are mainly illite.

The amount of NH_4^+ fixed by H_2O_2 untreated soils is also furnished in Table 2. The table shows that in all the cases the amount of fixation is greater than in the case of H_2O_2 treated soil and the fixation increases with the time of incubation. The native soils contain mineral part and organic matter part. The organic matter contains both nonhumic and humic substances. The humic substances because of the presence in their molecules of the active functional groups react with the clay to form clay humus complex. Stable complexes are formed either when the humic anion penetrates the coordination shell of an iron and aluminium atom in the surface of the hydroxide and becomes incorporated into the surface hydroxyl layer or by hydrogen bonding¹⁷. In soils, clay-humus complex both stable and unstable forms are present. When NH_4^+ ion is added to the native soils, clay as well as the organic matter weakly bound to clay fix the added NH_4^+ . But when humic acid is added in the system in pure form it quickly interacts with the clay fraction of the soil because of the presence in their structure the more active functional groups in comparison with the native soil organic matter and hinders the fixation of NH_4^+ . It also may form a protective coating on the clay surface because of its large surface area and thereby blocks the fixation sites of the clay. The decrease in fixation can also be explained in another way. In the present case, Silva and Bremner's method was used to estimate the fixed ammonium. In this process KOB_r was used to remove the organic matter part. If humic acid itself fixes the NH_4^+ in greater amount in comparison with the mineral part then the major portion of the fixed NH_4^+ will be removed by KOB_r treatment. There are good evidences¹⁸⁻²⁰ regarding the fixation of NH_4^+ by humic substances. Therefore, this supposition cannot be ruled out. But this needs further verification and the work is in progress. Nevertheless, the decrease in fixation with the increase of the amount of humic acid strongly supports this view. However, if it is actually the case then it has some practical importance. Because, the NH_4^+ fixed by clay minerals is practically unavailable to the plants. But NH_4^+ fixed by organic fractions of the soil will be released after mineralisation and will be available to the plants.

In the case of H_2O_2 treated soils the situation slightly changes. Hydrogen peroxide reacts not only with the weakly bound but also with the strongly bound native organic matter and in the course of the reaction the H_2O_2 molecule penetrates the lattices of the clays and thereby ruptures them. As a result the dimension of the space between the two plates most probably increases and therefore the added NH_4^+ does not fix so much and can be easily leached out by 1 N KCl solution.

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